

8th
ANNUAL
REPORT

for the year ending June 30, 1964

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

1025 Connecticut Avenue, N.W.
Washington, D. C. 20036

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* President Hard served as a member of the Executive Committee through November 13, 1963. He has been succeeded by Chancellor Wells.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

Late in 1960 the Ford Foundation approved a new grant of eight million dollars to enable the Council to continue for an additional seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems, and at the same time further to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

INTRODUCTORY

The past year was replete with developments, in which the Council had a share, of promise or accomplishment for library work.

Automation and the Library of Congress. On January 22, 1964 Dr. Gilbert W. King and his colleagues brought in the report bearing this title. It had been the object of their painstaking inquiry since March 1961, the original grant for the purpose going back, indeed, to October 1960. This document, of which a further account is given later,¹ at last opened the way for work toward the development of a national system in which the (general) research libraries of the country might be linked through the use of automatic devices. The Association of Research Libraries was quick to urge the Librarian of Congress to press forward along the lines suggested.

The immediate significance of the document was enhanced by its being nearly simultaneous with the important development mentioned in last year's report,² namely, the acquisition by the computer of the capability of commanding lower as well as upper case type, diacritics as well as Arabic numerals, and non-Latin as well as Roman characters through the use of chain printers, photocomposing machines and automatic typewriters. Although when the King report appeared there was no instance (with perhaps one exception) in which this new capability was actually in use on behalf of library work, there were several active programs for applying it to the production of catalog cards, catalogs in book form, and bibliographic compilations, and by midsummer 1964 the *Index Medicus* was about to be printed from computer-controlled photocomposition, performed at the rate of 300 characters a second.³

Given this capability, it was now possible to foresee the early availability of bibliographic information in machine-readable form, capable of meeting all predictable bibliographic and typographic needs. The Council, which had been im-

¹ P. 41, *infra*.

² VII: 9-11. (Citations in this form are to the Council's annual reports; in the present instance to its *Seventh Annual Report*, pages 9-11.)

³ Not 500 characters a minute, as stated at VII: 10.

patiently awaiting this opportunity, immediately took advantage of it, as reported later,⁴ in an attempt to develop standards for the machine-readable record.

The reasoning behind this action is as follows. The cost of preparation of the machine-readable record is a principal expense of automation of bibliographic operations and constitutes a principal obstacle to developments in this area. Consequently, if the preparation can be performed centrally so as to distribute the cost among a number of subscribers, much important experimentation and development may be expected to ensue which would otherwise not occur. But for the centrally-prepared record to be generally useful, compatibility must first obtain between the producing and using systems, and standardization is necessary to effect this.

Indeed, the situation today is in main issues identical with that of 1901 when the Library of Congress began its distribution of catalog cards. Then, as now, benefits of inestimable value were promised by a system of centralized cataloging; but these benefits were conditional upon the adoption of standards—the cataloging code, the typographic design of the catalog card, the very dimensions of the card. Because the principal elements were standardized in 1901 there is today a high degree of compatibility, both bibliographical and physical, between the catalogs of the largest and the smallest libraries in the country. But refinement of the standards has continued through the years, and it is interesting to observe now that the new inquiry into the standards of the machine-readable record raises questions that have been put to one side throughout the history of the centrally-produced printed catalog card.

The "Laboratory"—First Phase. Previous reports have recounted the steps taken by the Council to "concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel."⁵ These took the form of an investigation, directed by Dr. J. C. R. Licklider, on "concepts and problems of libraries of the future." The terminal report rendered at the conclusion of the second year of this investigation is described on a later page.⁶ It may be

⁴ P. 43, *infra*.

⁵ VI: 10; VII: 40-41.

⁶ P. 38, *infra*.

considered as completing a first phase of the work of the "laboratory," in which the problem has been exposed, its dimensions determined, the outlines of a solution hypothesized, and steps to the solution indicated. Meanwhile, the report itself has been announced for early publication.⁷

A New Shaw. The reference here is to *A List of Books for College Libraries* prepared by the librarian of Swarthmore College, Charles B. Shaw, for the American Library Association in 1931 under a grant from the Carnegie Corporation of New York. This list has served indispensably through the years — as the guide to acquisition which was its primary intention, as a touchstone of adequacy of college libraries, and as the starting point for every new list of the kind.

But the Shaw list was out of date on the day of publication, and although a supplement was provided in 1939 there has never been any serious attempt to make it genuinely and continuously current. Yet this is what is needed. Colleges, with their restricted funds and smaller library staffs and faculties, must select their acquisitions from the same enormous universe of publications as do the great university libraries with large book funds, expert book-selection staffs and large and specialized faculties. Even for the latter the means for evaluating new publications are very inefficient. What is needed, as was long since agreed, is a current book-selection service, suitable for the liberal arts college, which would provide at approximately monthly intervals brief but authoritative evaluations of current books, which might be accumulated from time to time to form a new basic list such as the Shaw.

Although, as explained later,⁸ this was easier said than done, during the past year there was the satisfaction of witnessing the publication, with good augury of success, of the first issues of a current book-selection service aimed at the college level.

National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. The gratifying progress made during the past year by the Library of Congress in this important project is recorded on later pages,⁹ where the story ends with the report that the Library was seeking statutory authorization and appropriation to carry

⁷ J. C. R. Licklider: *Concepts and Problems of Libraries of the Future*. Cambridge: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press. Announced for publication in September, 1964.

⁸ P. 19, *infra*.

⁹ P. 11, *infra*.

on the work. It can now be recorded that this was accomplished by the Legislative Branch Appropriation Act 1965, approved by the President August 20, 1964.

Summary of Operations in 1964. Thirty-nine grants, contracts and other allocations were made by the Council during the fiscal year 1964 in the amount of \$1,037,948. Twenty-eight of the allocations were for new projects; eleven were for extensions or renewals of previously-supported projects.

The following pages briefly describe the projects assisted during the past year, as well as the results of projects completed.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

I. BIBLIOGRAPHIC APPARATUS AND TECHNIQUES

(The ultimate objective of library work is to put into the hands of an inquirer a document or an item of information responding to his need. The techniques and apparatus by which the appropriate document or information is identified are those of bibliography. The apparatus includes systems of classification, catalogs, indexes and bibliographies of many kinds, including new varieties in the form of punched cards and computers. The techniques include the arts both of constructing and using the apparatus. A number of the Council's projects during the past year have been concerned with improvement or development in both areas.)

The undertakings represented by the projects discussed in this chapter are nothing if not important. Here are reported the creation of monumental catalogs and registers of research material of first importance, the codification and refinement of rules for improving the creation of bibliographic information, the investigation of electronic systems for handling such information and for assisting the intellectual operation of subject analysis. Here, finally, are listed important projects involving the selection of books for the purposes of higher and professional education.

The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, after decades of hope on the part of scholars, began to assume reality when late in 1958 the Council made the first of a series of grants to the Library of Congress for the purpose.¹⁰ The *Catalog* is being prepared by the Library with the cooperation of institutions with manuscript holdings in all parts of the nation. Initially, the entries are printed as catalog cards, but as work progresses the cards are being reproduced for publication in book form as a commercial venture without cost to the project. This past spring the second volume of the *Catalog* and a cumulated index volume to the first and second volumes

¹⁰ III: 19-21; VI: 13-14; VII: 8-9.

were published.¹¹ Since the subject matter of history is all embracing, the index reveals such disparate entries as those for: Tennessee Valley Authority, Winnebago Indians, camels, Home Missionary Daughters of Northern California, Socialist Newspaper Union, Samuel Langhorne Clemens, Electric Boat Company, John Muir, and, Hessians in the American Revolution. With publication of the second volume, a total of 12,324 collections have been described and indexed, and 81 additional repositories, as of then, had joined in the collective effort, making a total of 398 participating repositories in 46 states.

Since the appearance of the second volume, reports on 2,400 additional collections were received, of which 1,935 had been revised for the catalog before the end of the year.

The importance, for the purposes of historical research, of providing bibliographical access to the thousands of collections of letters, diaries and other personal papers, business records and manuscript materials dispersed in depositories throughout the country is obvious. Yet the task was so huge and the difficulties so numerous that an effective beginning had to await the ample kind of support which the Council provided in 1958.

This type of task is never completed, however, and although the Council made two supplementary grants it could not continue to assist indefinitely. Nevertheless, with the back of the job substantially broken, the future requirements should be for completing the record of existing collections and adding that of new acquisitions as they occur. For these purposes the Library has included an item in its estimates for the new fiscal year.

Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada. "Serials" is the term used in libraries to describe magazines, reports or other publications which appear recurrently. As an estimated half million separate serials have appeared since the early 18th century and since no collection

¹¹ *The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, 1962.* Compiled by The Library of Congress . . . from reports provided by American repositories. Hamden, Connecticut: The Shoe String Press, Inc., 1964. x, 532 p. And: *The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, Index 1959-1962* . . . v, 732 p.

(The first volume:) *The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, 1959-1961* . . . Ann Arbor, Michigan: J. W. Edwards, Inc., 1962. viii, 1061 p.

contains more than a fraction of the total, reliance must be placed upon inter-library loan. For this, a knowledge of what exists, and where, is essential. Abroad, attempts at local inter-library cataloging of serials began more than a century ago. In the United States a list of the holdings in eight Baltimore libraries was compiled as early as 1876. Other local lists subsequently appeared here and in 1927 a general compilation, the *Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada*, was published. This was followed by two supplements and a second, larger edition, which was also followed by two supplements, the last in 1953.

The original work had been done under the auspices of the American Library Association, but in 1948 the then recently organized Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials assumed the responsibility for the *Union List* previously borne by the A.L.A. Advisory Committee. So great is the proliferation of serials—an estimated some 8,000 new publications each year—that the second edition and supplements were obsolete almost upon publication. The Council therefore in 1959 made a grant to the Joint Committee, an incorporated, non-profit organization, for preparation of a third edition,¹² and a supplementary grant this past year. Following publication of the third edition, it is expected that additions will be recorded in *New Serial Titles*, published by the Library of Congress.

The first edition of the *Union List* was a book of 1,580 pages and listed 75,000 titles held by more than 225 libraries. The third edition will be in five volumes, containing about 5,000 pages and including 148,887 titles and cross references in 956 North American libraries. The work is being published for the Joint Committee by the H. W. Wilson Company, of New York, publisher of the first two editions. The printer is the British firm of Balding & Mansell, printer of the British Museum's *General Catalogue of Printed Books*. The firm is using its perhaps unique sequential camera, which may result in saving as much as \$100,000, and the book is being printed on a British acid-free paper, Wolvercote. Printing is expected to be completed sometime in 1965.

Economics of Catalogs in Book Form. Stanford University, with a new undergraduate library building under construction,

¹² III: 21-23.

has been assembling a collection with which to stock it. An initial collection of 40,000 titles in 60,000 volumes is assumed with perhaps 10,000 titles being added annually until the collection reaches 100,000 volumes. Inclining toward a catalog in printed book form, copies of which could be available on each floor of the library, be distributed about the campus, and perhaps be made available in subject parts for purchase by students, Stanford was desirous of knowing the comparative economics of the several methods of producing book catalogs and also how they compare in cost with card catalogs. As this information is of interest to a number of institutions, the Council made a grant to the University this past year for a study. The study has been completed and a report prepared.¹³

Six basic methods for producing catalogs in book form are examined. These are: reproduction of Library of Congress cards by photo offset from shingled copy; reproduction from cards specially typed and shingled; reproduction from typed pages; reproduction from tab cards; reproduction from copy prepared for sequential cameras; and, reproduction by means of several forms of computer composition. Alternatives for several methods are also dealt with. Time and cost factors are analyzed. Information is also expressed in algebraic form.

Cataloging Codes. A previous grant to the American Library Association to forward work on its Catalog Code Revision Project¹⁴ was supplemented with another appropriation this past year. The work represents not only a revision of the Anglo-American Catalog Code of 1908 in the light of the agreements reached by the International Conference on Cataloging Principles held in Paris in 1961, but an increase in scope as a result of incorporating the Rules for Descriptive Cataloging. The Library of Congress, which released the chief of its Descriptive Cataloging Division, Mr. Sumner Spalding, to serve as editor, is participating with the A.L.A. in the project. Other national library associations in the United States have designated consultants.

Since the work is international in approach, the Canadian Library Association is represented by personal membership

¹³ R. M. Hayes and R. M. Shoffner: *The Economics of Book Catalog Production, A Study Prepared for Stanford University Libraries . . .* [Sherman Oaks, California: Advanced Information Systems Division, Hughes Dynamics, Inc.] 1964. 110 p. Processed. Copies available from Stanford University Libraries.

¹⁴ V: 16; VII: 16.

on the Advisory Board and has appointed a committee to consider drafts. The (British) Library Association's Sub-Committee on Cataloguing Rules has been similarly participating, and copies of drafts have been submitted to the library associations of Australia and New Zealand.

The International Cataloguing Code Commission of the International Association of Music Libraries meets in Aarhus, Denmark, in August 1964 in connection with work on the *Rules for Full Cataloging of Music*. A grant has been made to the Music Library Association to enable it to send a representative, Mrs. Virginia Cunningham, to the meeting. Mrs. Cunningham, Head of the Music Section of the Descriptive Cataloging Division at the Library of Congress, has for several years been at work for the Commission on a draft of full cataloging rules.

Governmental Cataloging Rules. Several agencies of the Federal Government have developed important bibliographical services with respect to the technical publications within their fields of interest. However, due to parochialism, the cataloging rules used by these agencies have been at variance both with those of each other and of the library world, with the result that their cataloging is either useless to libraries generally, or at the very least is incompatible with the cataloging ordinarily employed by these libraries.

Recently the Federal agencies moved to standardize among themselves, and the Committee on Scientific and Technical Information of the Federal Council for Science and Technology consequently issued a *Standard for Descriptive Cataloging of Government Scientific and Technical Reports*.¹⁵ The Council on Library Resources has made a small appropriation to enable the Association of Research Libraries to bring the representatives of the Government and of the library world together with a view to harmonizing differences.

Original vs. Centralized Cataloging. Some years ago the Dawson study¹⁶ showed the extent to which a number of representative American research libraries were dependent for their cataloging operations upon the Library of Congress cata-

¹⁵ PB (Publication Board) 181605, December 1963. For sale by Office of Technical Services, U. S. Department of Commerce.

¹⁶ John Minto Dawson: *The Acquisitions and Cataloging of Research Libraries: A Study of the Possibilities for Centralized Processing.* *The Library Quarterly* 27: 1-22, January 1957.

logging cards and the extent to which, when these cards were not available, each library was compelled to generate its own cataloging information.

The Association of Research Libraries is currently seeking, as a primary project, to reduce the amount of this original cataloging which, according to a recent informal survey, forms on the average 46 per cent of the cataloging of each library, costing almost four times as much as cataloging performed with the use of Library of Congress cataloging copy.

The significance of this inquiry lies in the fact that the members of the Association are now spending about 16 per cent of their operating budgets, amounting to approximately \$18 million annually, on cataloging, but in spite of this their cataloging arrears have increased 160 per cent in the last decade. A method for substantially increasing the proportion of centrally assisted cataloging would effect significant savings to these (as well as other) libraries and benefits to their users through reductions of backlogs. The Council has made a small grant to the Association to update the Dawson study (with Dr. Dawson's assistance) as the first step in this inquiry.

Spanish Subject Heading List. Library work in Latin America has long suffered from the lack of a standard list of subject headings with which to effect subject organization of collections. Each library, if it is to have one, is compelled to make its own list, with consequent waste of effort, lack of uniformity and less than optimum results. A grant to the Pan American Union will make it possible to develop a list superior to any now existing which will, besides, promote uniformity of practice. For the preparation of the printer's copy of this list it is proposed to use composing machines actuated by perforated paper tape; this is expected to encourage production of future revised editions by minimizing the effort and expense both of compilation and publication.

Indexing and Abstracting. The Council's support of research looking to the possibility of enlisting the assistance of computers in the subject indexing of text has been previously reported.¹⁷ The most recent inquiry of this kind to receive the Council's support — that of the American Bar Foundation reported last year¹⁸ — is investigating the possibility of the machine indexing of case law. One of the larger items in the

¹⁷ IV: 23-24; V, 15-16; VII: 12-13, 54.

¹⁸ VII:13. See also William B. Eldridge and Sally F. Dennis: The Computer as a Tool for Legal Research. *Jurimetrics* 28: 78-99, Winter 1963.

budget for this inquiry provides for recording on computer tape the text of some 5,000 Federal cases from the *North-eastern Reporter*.

It is obvious that the same machine-readable text may serve a number of investigators, and a stipulation of the grant was that copies of the tape should be made available at cost for use in research. Among the takers have been the Southwest Legal Foundation, at Dallas, and the College of Law, University of Illinois.

Members of the Information Technology Division (formerly Data Processing Systems Division) of the National Bureau of Standards have been conducting some small scale experiments in automatic (or machine) indexing based on statistical association techniques termed "SADSACT" (Self-Assigned Descriptors from Self And Cited Titles). Since preliminary work has indicated that the method may compare favorably with other automatic indexing techniques which usually require more input text, more machine processing or more human intervention, a small grant has been made to the Bureau to support further machine tests and evaluation.

A grant has also been made this past year to the Library Association, London, to enable Mr. H. Allan Whatley, F.L.A., Editor of *Library Science Abstracts* and Lecturer at the Scottish School of Librarianship, Scottish College of Commerce, in Glasgow, to visit and observe the major indexing and abstracting services for library science and documentation in the United States and on the European continent.

Computer Control of Serial Records. "Serials," in library terminology, are all publications which, like periodicals, bulletins, transactions, etc., are published sequentially. The serial record division in a large library characteristically includes such activities as checking in new issues and routing them to their appropriate destinations, claiming missing issues, title pages and tables of contents, maintaining the record of volumes forwarded for binding, renewing and paying for subscriptions, and giving information on all these activities. Seemingly simple and routine, the operation is actually complex and costly and has resisted attempts to simplify it.

The Library of the University of California, San Diego at La Jolla, several years ago began an investigation of the feasibility of reducing serial record work to a largely computerized operation. The first results were promising so the

Council made a grant to further the investigation.¹⁹ The project has been completed and a report prepared.²⁰ The investigation indicates that serial control by computer in libraries with 2,000 to 10,000 serials is feasible; for libraries with fewer serials it is probably not practical unless inexpensive computer facilities are readily available; and, for libraries with more than 15,000 or 20,000 serials, or rapidly growing toward that level, it would probably be most efficient to divide the system into parts to reduce the length of tapes.

The manpower costs in operating a computerized system appear to be comparable to those of a manual system, it was found, but the machine costs are more than offset by savings in having information on holdings readily available to patrons, in the positive arrangements for claiming missing issues of periodicals, in improved bindery routines, and in improved access to serials information in all departments and units of the library.

Book Selection Lists — Law. While the library of one of the 109 members of the American Association of Law Schools exceeds a million volumes, sixteen have fewer than 30,000. To promote the strengthening of the libraries and hence the teaching programs of the member schools, the Association, with assistance from the Council, has employed Dr. Miles O. Price to prepare a series of basic lists of books especially appropriate and requisite for a law school library. Dr. Price, who formerly headed the Columbia University law school library and also served as a professor of law at the University, will be assisted by consultants in special subjects, volunteer reviewers and an advisory committee. The book selection lists will be annotated and indicate first, second and third preferences for acquisition. The initial list is expected to describe an Anglo-American law collection of approximately 60,000 volumes. Subsequent lists will be concerned with foreign, international, and comparative law. Altogether the lists will describe an "optimum" collection of about 200,000 recom-

¹⁹ VII: 15-16.

²⁰ *Final Report Serials Computer Project, May 1964, University Library and Computer Center.* La Jolla, University of California, San Diego. 209 1. Processed. Also: George Vdovin, Melvin J. Voigt, David Newman and Clay Perry: *Computer Processing of Serials. Library Resources and Technical Services* 7: 71-80, Winter 1963. Melvin J. Voigt: *The Costs of Data Processing in University Libraries — In Serials Handling. College and Research Libraries* 24: 489-491. November 1963.

mended volumes toward which smaller libraries can work and against which the larger libraries can check their holdings. The lists, which will not be a duplication of the catalogs of the most extensive collections, are expected to be completed by the beginning of 1966. Thereafter the Association plans to continue the program for at least five years, at its own expense, by adding new publications to the lists.

Lewis and Clark College, in Portland, Oregon, conducts an overseas program in which undergraduates are sent to foreign countries for a year's residence, study and work. Its program has been handicapped by the lack of adequate bibliographies for the use of students preparing to go abroad. The Council has made a grant to enable preparation of a pilot bibliography of materials on Japan by Dr. Hideo Hashimoto, chairman of the College's Department of Religion. It is believed that the bibliographies may be of use to other colleges with area study programs.

A New Shaw. The need for a "New Shaw," a book selection list for the use of college libraries in building their collections and keeping them up to date, has been narrated in previous annual reports.²¹ In April 1959 at a meeting in Chicago sponsored by the Council it was concluded that despite the urgent need of a basic volume which would bring up to date Charles B. Shaw's *A List of Books for College Libraries*, published in 1931, an even more pressing need was for a current weekly or monthly service providing succinct reviews of new publications by reviewers of authority. These reviews might, in time, afford the substance of a new basic volume.

The need and the requirement for its fulfilment were clear; the principal obstacle to achievement was budgetary. For while a basic list such as the Shaw can be produced at any time that there is a subsidy available, a current service cannot expect to remain indefinitely subsidized but must become self-supporting. And while the primary market for such a service consists of only approximately two thousand collegiate institutions, the number of books to be evaluated runs into many thousands. Under these circumstances it appeared that a current service either would price itself out of the market, or, if it should avoid that fate by cutting costs, would end by being inadequate as a reviewing journal.

²¹ III: 25-26; IV: 15; VI: 16.

At this point the Council undertook the New Shaw problem and spent a year in exploring the conditions of editing, manufacturing and marketing, as well as the relations between the current service and the cumulative basic list, which might permit support in achieving eventual self-support. Only when these conditions were satisfied in theory (as the result of taking advantage of new technological developments in editorial compilation and printing) was the project in November 1961 committed to the sponsorship of the Association of College and Research Libraries of the American Library Association under terms which provide a subsidy for the first four years' operation in anticipation of full self-support beginning with the fifth year. The Association in its turn commenced the search for an editor, an editorial office, etc.

In June 1963 the Association simultaneously announced the project, the designation of an Editorial Board, the appointment of an editor, Mr. Richard K. Gardner, the location of the editorial office in the Olin Library, Wesleyan University, and a contest for the name of the new journal. (This resulted in the title *Choice*, independently suggested by four contestants.) The target date for the first issue was set at March 1964.

The first issue of *Choice* appeared on date. It was prepared by Varityping on IBM punched cards, photographed by a Listomatic sequential camera, with final printing by photo offset. Experience with the first issue, however, indicated that the sequential camera technique, while suitable for bibliographies, listings or directories, is impractical for a journal with reviews running from six to thirty lines. Therefore, Photon composition, another cold type method, was substituted for the second and succeeding issues.

Choice will be published in 11 issues a year. It expects to carry reviews of 2,500 or more books annually. Review coverage for the present is limited to American publications in the fields of the basic liberal arts curriculum, and no coverage is now attempted of works in the fields of professional and pre-professional curricula such as law, medicine, nursing and home economics. About 1,300 reviewer/consultants, typically members of liberal arts college faculties, have been recruited on an unpaid basis. The journal has received an appreciative welcome from the library world and has gained the needed support of advertisers.

II. PHYSICAL ACCESS

(The bibliographic apparatus is merely a means to an end. Ultimately, the cited manuscript, book or periodical must be seen and consulted, either in original form or in some acceptable facsimile.)

The library arrangements which make it possible for a documentary record actually to lie under the eye of the inquirer include (among others) the steps by which the document was initially acquired by the library in original or copy; the further steps by which it was stored and preserved in a state of usefulness; and (in many cases) the still further steps by which a usable copy was once again made for the inquirer's use.

All of these steps — acquisition, storage, preservation, and copying for initial distribution and acquisition or for use — are represented among the projects initiated or completed last year.

Acquisitions — Africa. With the exception of the Union of South Africa, it is most difficult to collect material published in the countries south of the Sahara. There is no organized book trade, no current national bibliography to indicate what is being published, no counterpart funds as in India and the Middle East which can be used to support a Public Law 480 type of procurement program making use of indigenous staff, and the scantiness of publication makes it economically infeasible for American booksellers to send an agent through the area periodically to collect materials as is done in Latin America for American libraries. A small grant to the Association of Research Libraries made it possible for the Association's Farmington Plan Subcommittee on Africa to hold a conference at the Library of Congress in November 1963 to review the procurement problem and to plan solutions.

Acquisitions — Government Documents. Public Law 87-579, Depository Library Act of 1962, provided that the Superintendent of Documents should supply depository libraries with copies of Federal publications printed outside the Government Printing Office as well as those printed there. The House Appropriations Committee, however, eliminated the Printing Office's request for an appropriation for this purpose for the fiscal year 1964 on the grounds that the non-GPO material is

of doubtful value. In denying the request, the Committee asked for further information about non-GPO publications. The Council made a grant to the American Library Association to assist the preparation of a list, limited to 1963 publications, under the supervision of Mr. Jennings Wood, chief of the Exchange and Gift Division of the Library of Congress.

Acquisitions — Scholarly Photocopying. The photocopy has had an effect upon the availability of research materials comparable only to that of printing. It has made it possible for an investigator, without moving from his desk, to make use of material which just yesterday was available only to a person with unlimited time and funds for travel. It has, by the same token, made it possible to assemble in one place (or more) a corpus of material of which the parts are fragmented and scattered in libraries and archives in many countries.

Yet the scholarly and library world is still learning to live with the photocopy, and particularly with the microcopy, and the exploitation of these important copying techniques has hitherto been less than ideal. Indeed, the Council's support of the American Historical Association's *Guide to Photocopied Historical Materials in the United States and Canada* was expressly with the intention, among others, of ascertaining the extent to which photocopying has led to a new fragmenting and scattering of resources, and to correction of this tendency.

Accordingly, as the *Guide* was approaching publication in 1961 the American Council of Learned Societies, acting upon the suggestion of principal officers of several of its constituent societies including the American Historical Association and the Modern Language Association, accepted sponsorship of a study looking to the identification of criteria for establishing priorities for scholarly photocopying projects.²² A report, based on a study by Dr. Lester K. Born, is to be published in *PMLA* in September 1964, with preprints available several months earlier.²³ Its recommendations specify machinery for coordinating the planning of photocopying projects planned, underway, or completed. While the emphasis is on photocopying in foreign repositories, the recommendations are equally applicable to the

²² IV: 17.

²³ Planning for Scholarly Photocopying; A Report Prepared for the American Council of Learned Societies. *PMLA, Publications of the Modern-Language-Association-of-America* 79: 1-14, September 1964. Preprinted June 1964.

domestic situation. It is obvious that no solution can be satisfactory that neglects either.²⁴

Copying—Devices, Methods, Programs, Problems. Libraries exist by virtue of copying, and it has been said that they exist solely for the purpose of furnishing copies — mental or physical. However this may be, many of the Council's programs deal with copying. In addition to those mentioned immediately below, others are described in the next chapter in connection with testing and other administrative programs.²⁵

MICROPHOTO COPYING IN THE LIBRARY. Pages of a book or magazine placed face down on the window at the top of the above machine, at the push of a button, are photographed and printed within seconds at 12 x reduction on a 3" x 5" card inserted on the slide below. The card can be re-inserted at a later time for additional images — 12 in all. The machine, "Midax," utilizes Xerographic techniques.

Copying—Micro-Xerography. In 1960 the Council contracted with Bell and Howell Company to produce a step-and-

²⁴ V: 19, 42.

²⁵ P. 34, *infra*.

repeat camera for inexpensively making microcards or microfiches (i.e., transparent microcards) by a dry and immediate process not requiring laboratory processing.²⁶ The project has progressed to the stage where a prototype is undergoing field testing in the John Crerar Library in Chicago.

The machine, known as "Midax," is capable of photographically copying the open pages of a book or magazine, including halftone illustrations, at 12 x reduction, on a 3" x 5" card or transparency, using Xerographic techniques. Ease of operation is one of its outstanding features. The material to be copied is placed face down on a window at the top of the machine. The cellulose acetate transparency is placed in a slide over a mark which indicates where on the surface of the transparency the photographic image is to be located. About 30 to 35 seconds after a button is pushed by the operator the image has been printed on the card. Additional images can be added at the time or later by simply moving the card to a new position. This "add-an-image" capability permits a four-page article, say, to be copied at one time and an eight-page article on the same subject to be added at a later time, the cards accommodating 12 images in all. The images are not susceptible to fading. As it is easier to learn to operate the machine than most office equipment, personnel costs are expected to be slight.

The resolution obtained in the images produced by this prototype has been so gratifying (approximately 130 lines per mm.) that the manufacturers are preparing the second version with a capability of 20 x reduction.

Copying — An Inexpensive Micro-Projector. In another action the Council contracted with Photo Devices, Inc., of Rochester, New York, for a design study looking toward the development of an inexpensive microcopy viewer, or projector, suitable for purchase by the individual. Ideally, such a device would be portable, be self-powered (batteries), take 35 mm. and 16 mm. roll film and sheet film, have magnification between 10 x and 20 x, and be usable in a normally lighted room. The study will seek to identify the principal elements of design and manufacture.

Copying — An Inexpensive Reader-Printer. Reader-printers are projectors which are used for viewing microcopies but which possess the additional capability of producing enlarged

²⁶ V: 24-25.

paper prints of particular microimages as desired. Of the reader-printers on the market, none is portable or costs less than about six hundred dollars. Following demonstration of a reader-printer promising the virtues of both portability and low cost, the Council contracted with Documentation Incorporated, of Bethesda, Maryland, for the manufacture of seven of the devices. When constructed, the working models will be tested in libraries under conditions of actual use.

Copying — A Scholar's Camera. A device with which an investigator might conveniently make copies of pages of text or illustration needed for his studies has been a long-felt desideratum. To meet the requirements of convenience the device should be easily portable, should not ordinarily require special illumination for its use, should be able to display its product almost immediately (before the original is reshelved) without waiting for laboratory processing, and should be inexpensive to purchase and operate.

In 1961, to ascertain how closely these requirements might be met with "off-the-shelf" technology, the Council commissioned from the Bell and Howell Company a copying camera for scholarly use.²⁷ This camera weighed three pounds; it had a folding stand which controlled the target area, distance and ratio of reduction (10 x); it used a fine-grain black-and-white 35 mm. film obtainable at any drugstore and usable under ordinary available light conditions; and it had an attachable cassette in which the film could be processed with a monobath immediately following exposure. However, although possessing characteristics of elegance in design, the achievement did not justify further prosecution; the soft monobath processing gave resolution of only 3.5 lines per mm. of the target material, processing was fussy, tedious and unreliable, and the cost of operation was 4.5 to 13 cents per page (i.e. 9 to 26 cents per two-page exposure) depending on whether the film was processed ten exposures or one exposure at a time.

Copying — Another Scholar's Camera. Accordingly, in a second attempt, the Council contracted in 1963 with Photogrammetry, Inc. for the breadboard model of a camera using Polaroid film.²⁸ In order to reduce the cost per exposure (which would have approximated 25 cents at the drugstore

²⁷ VI: 30.

²⁸ VII: 28.

price if the full area of the film had been used) the manufacturer developed a sliding lens-board which made possible four exposures on a single film. The camera weighed $4\frac{7}{8}$ pounds; again a folding stand established the target area, distance and reduction-ratio (4 x); the enormous speed of the Polaroid film eliminated any need for supplemental illumination, and the results of the copying could of course be viewed within seconds and without fuss following exposure.

Again, however, the results did not justify immediate exploitation of the development. The low resolving capability of the Polaroid film, even at 4 x reduction, permitted the resolution of only 4.5 lines per mm. of the original; and this combined with its low contrast was insufficient. The cost of operation was approximately 8 cents per page in groups of four.

Copying — The "Copywriter." Previous reports have recorded attempts to develop a device by which passages of text might be copied with the use of a hand-held scanning instrument.²⁹ The first attempt resulted in too clumsy a machine. A second attempt has commenced with a feasibility report, submitted during the year by The Institute for Scientific Information of Philadelphia which has explored the possibility of achieving greater portability through the use of minute photo-cells, printed circuits and a Xerographic recorder.³⁰

Copying for Distribution — Microstorage in Crystals. A preliminary investigation of the recording, storage at high resolution and reading-out of graphic information, utilizing the "crystal color center" phenomenon occurring in certain crystals, was reported last year.³¹ The Carson Laboratories, of Bristol, Connecticut, have completed an initial demonstration of the feasibility of information storage in these crystals.³² A microfilm image having 100 lines resolution per mm. was stored full size in a crystal and was later read out full size on microfilm. The latter retained 51 lines per mm. resolution. Also, the Laboratories have learned a number of important things about crystals, including methods for avoiding decay of stored information at room temperatures and methods of annealing crystals using radio frequencies instead of heat. In view of

²⁹ III: 38; IV: 30; VII: 28.

³⁰ Institute for Scientific Information, Philadelphia: *Feasibility Study & Report on Copywriter*. Philadelphia, 1963. 18 p. Processed.

³¹ VII: 27-28.

³² Carson Laboratories, Bristol, Connecticut: *Demonstration of High-Density Crystalline Photo-Storage*. Bristol, 1963. 22 p. Processed.

the progress made in the initial program, the Council has contracted with the Laboratories for further investigation of what may prove to be an inexpensive method of disseminating information.

ENLARGEMENT FROM CRYSTAL STORAGE. The page above began with a microfilm copy of an approximately $7\frac{1}{8} \times 10\frac{1}{8}$ " page from the Journal of the Physical Society of Japan, 1960. The microfilm dimensions were $\frac{5}{8} \times 29/32$ ", a reduction of about 11.3 times. In experimental work at the Carson Laboratories, the image was stored in a crystal with an additional overall reduction of about 17 times. The image was then retrieved and the above 8×10 " photographic print—representing a slight enlargement of the original page—was made. With each generation of the image there was some loss of resolution.

Copying for Distribution to Blind Readers. Not excepting Braille, the principal means of providing reading material for the blind consists of long-playing phonograph records. These

are, however, expensive, heavy, subject to abrasion and other damage, and difficult and costly to store, transport and service. In the fall of 1960 the Council made two simultaneous, related grants: one to the Library of Congress and one to Recording for the Blind, Inc., for a pilot project leading to development of a device to enable blind readers to use inexpensive, long-playing magnetic tape recordings and making possible easy mechanical duplication of such tapes by the Library of Congress' Division for the Blind or others.³³ The work on both developments was performed for the grantee institutions by Columbia Broadcasting System Laboratories.

A tape-multiplier has been made for the Library of Congress, and a report prepared.³⁴ The multiplier, which can make 10 copies simultaneously and to which additional copying units can be added if desirable, is ready and waits only upon the completion of the reproducing device.

Work on this device, a cartridge tape player, has been slower. CBS Laboratories have developed a prototype, however, for Recording for the Blind.³⁵ It is small (9 inches wide, 13.5 inches long, 6 inches high), will thread the tape automatically and contains the controls necessary for use by the blind. Developed with it is a cartridge which may be handled and stored and the enclosed tape played without risk of damage from handling. This cartridge, 5 inches in diameter, holds 10 hours of recording and is said to be capable of holding 24 hours if a thinner tape is used. In the present prototype the player is too heavy, complicated and expensive. Another attempt is to be made with the hope of overcoming these drawbacks.

The Storage Problem — "Selective Book Retirement" at Yale. The space problems, created by the notorious tendency of research library collections to double in size approximately every 16 years, have been mentioned previously in these reports, as well as various measures undertaken to contend with them.³⁶ Following a meeting in 1958 to plan investigations in

³³ V: 25.

³⁴ *Tape Duplicator for Magnetic Talking Books. Final Report — Instruction Manual. Report No. CLD-1518 . . . Prepared for Library of Congress . . . GBS Laboratories, Stamford, Connecticut, August 13 1962.* [46] p., 11 plates. 29 cm.

³⁵ *Recording for the Blind, Inc., New York: Final Report, Cartridge Tape Player.* New York, 1964. 3 p. Ill. Typescript.

³⁶ III: 32-33; V: 31-32.

this field, two studies were launched. One, at the University of Chicago Library, was to seek patterns in the use of books which might supply criteria for assigning space priorities to various categories, and a report of this was published, in a limited preliminary edition, in 1961.³⁷ The second, at Yale University, has sought to demonstrate the operation of a "compact" storage operation and to develop the bases upon which it could rest. The report of this study was published this past year.³⁸

In the "Selective Book Retirement Program" which is the subject of the Yale report, books which are adjudged to have least expectancy of use are removed from the subject-arranged open-access shelves and placed in "compact" storage. There they can no longer be found by "browsing," and only by call-number obtained from the catalog; but the efficiency of space utilization is increased nearly five times (from 14 to 64 volumes per square foot) while the per-volume cost of construction was reduced from \$1.68 to 42 cents.

Tests made during the course of the study showed that few of the books condemned to "selective retirement" were ever called for; indeed, only 3 $\frac{1}{3}$ per cent (or not quite 6,000 of the 180,000 volumes in the collection) were requested during a two-year period. Several expectations of the study were unfulfilled: to gain the collaboration of the faculty in a study of the bases of selection for retirement ("a library can depend upon faculty members to assist in book retirement or in book selection only in rare cases"); to ascertain what arrangements might be made to compensate for the loss of immediacy; to study the effectiveness of the program in stabilizing the size of the collection ("at Yale, at least, it would be very difficult to do this"). Thus, further studies will be needed.

Preservation — The W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. The Laboratory was established in August 1961 in the building of the Virginia State Historical Society, in Richmond, to serve exclusively for research and development in the interest of preservation of library materials. This past year the Council, which was instrumental in the establishment of the Labora-

³⁷ Herman H. Fussler and Julian L. Simon: *Patterns in the Use of Books in Large Research Libraries . . .* [Chicago:] The University of Chicago Library, 1961. xi, 283, [42] p. Processed.

³⁸ Lee Ash: *Yale's Selective Book Retirement Program.* [New Haven, Connecticut:] Archon Books, 1963. xii, 94 p. (Shoe String Press, Inc., Hamden, Connecticut, distributor.)

tory,³⁹ unique of its kind, again made an appropriation for the support of its work.

The activities of the Laboratory fall into the following categories:

- Continued examination and testing of old papers with a view to ascertaining what has actually happened to paper-and-ink records and what in consequence may be expected of them and required for them in the future.
- Development of techniques and materials for delaying deterioration in existing library stock. (Especially, work on an aerosol deacidification process.)
- Development of materials and methods for effecting improved permanence/durability of records, as well as improvement in their other characteristics. (Especially, work on an adhesive for “perfect” (adhesive) library bookbinding.)
- Development of performance standards for library binding (including the testing to establish such standards).
- Development of test methods and apparatus in connection with all of the above.

A number of these aspects of the Laboratory's work were covered in a report of its first two years,⁴⁰ published in 1963, which constituted the first issue in a series. Two further issues, now in press, will carry the account further, and add significantly to the available body of published test data on the several topics. Meanwhile, also, further contributions of the Laboratory to testing technique have appeared in professional and trade journals.⁴¹ A number of other articles have described the work of the Laboratory.⁴²

³⁹ VI: 21-22; VII: 20-23.

⁴⁰ W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Richmond, Virginia: *Permanence/Durability of the Book: A Two-Year Research Program*. Richmond, 1963. 46 p.

⁴¹ W. J. Barrow: “Accelerated Aging Study of Several Writing Papers” — Re-Evaluation of Data. *Tappi (Technical Association of the Pulp and Paper Industry)* 47: 105-7, February 1964.

———: New Device Tests Performance of Library Bindings. *Book Production* 79: 60-62, March 1964.

⁴² Sylvia Auerbach: Coming: Books That Won't Crumble. *Economics and Business Bulletin of the School of Business Administration, Temple University* 16: 26-28, March, 1964.

Verner W. Clapp: “Permanent/Durable” Book Papers. *ALA (American Library Association) Bulletin* 57: 847-52, October 1963.

Virginius Dabney: New Ways to Permanent Files. *Saturday Review* 87-8, May 9, 1964.

[William Francis:] Rags to Riches; The Story of Virginia Paper-making. *Arts in Virginia (Virginia Museum of Fine Arts)* 4: 3-26, Spring 1964.

Lee E. Grove: The Conservation of Paper. *Museum News (Journal of the American Association of Museums)* 42: 15-20, October 1963.

Preservation — Performance Standards for Library Binding.
The Barrow Laboratory has continued its work for the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association on the development of standards for library bookbinding, to be

TESTING BINDING ADHESIVES. Binding cements, found by the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory to be non-injurious to paper and to offer good life expectancy, are tested for workability in the bindery of the Catholic University of America Libraries. The experimental clamp binder shown was developed by Mid-Atlantic Associates, Inc., for use in instances where volumes, because of random size and thickness, do not lend themselves to inexpensive production line methods.

written in terms of the performance required of bindings for various purposes, e.g., children's books, reference books, etc. The task presented was not the less difficult in that until after its inception there was no testing equipment which could reproduce in the laboratory the effects of natural wear and tear of library use on bookbindings, that there are no accepted quantitative measures (in terms of years, withdrawals from the shelf, circulations, or other units) which might provide a scale of adequacy or satisfactory performance of a bookbinding, and that for all but a few forms of bound books (e.g. telephone books, children's books, school textbooks) it usually takes many years of shelf life or normal use to reduce a bound book to unusability.

Accordingly, while examining many thousands of no-longer-usable bindings to identify the points at which breakdown occurred, the Laboratory simultaneously developed two devices

for simulating the results of natural deterioration. These are described in the biennial report to which previous reference has been made,⁴³ and one — the Universal Tester — has been the subject of an article in the trade literature.⁴⁴ Meanwhile, the Library Technology Project, with the assistance of a special advisory committee for this project, has placed copies of a number of identical books in hard-usage situations, such as the reserve rooms of university libraries and in children's libraries. There their performance in use can be measured within reasonable periods. Although it is necessarily a slow business to assemble test data of this kind, yet it is felt that it will soon be possible to draft at least the preliminary standards in performance terms.

⁴³ Footnote No. 40.

⁴⁴ Footnote No. 41.

III. LIBRARY ADMINISTRATION

(Here are discussed projects which intend the improvement of the arrangements by which the means of bibliographic assistance and those which provide physical access to documentary sources of information are brought to the service of the reader. Examples are the planning of library buildings, training of staff, standardizing and testing of library materials and supplies, and legal problems affecting photocopying.)

The Library Technology Project. The Council during the past year continued its support of the Library Technology Project.⁴⁵ LTP, established in 1959 and operating under the auspices of the American Library Association, directly and through assignment seeks to apply contemporary technology and recent scientific discovery to library operations and services and to disseminate its findings to the library profession. Tests and evaluations of equipment and supplies, systems studies, development of performance standards for matériel, and an individualized information service giving purchasing suggestions are among its activities. Reports are also published in a monthly column appearing in the *ALA Bulletin* and in *Special Libraries* and in separate publication. Beginning in January 1965, a bimonthly information service, to be called "Library Technology Reports," will be published on a subscription basis which is expected to make it self-supporting.

Insuring the Library. The publication by LTP of the volume *Protecting the Library and Its Resources*, resulting from an extensive study of the subject commissioned from a firm of insurance engineers, was reported last year.⁴⁶ This volume, actually a manual of practice, included a model insurance policy. During the past year the American Library Association's Insurance for Libraries Committee has interested a leading insurance group in writing a policy nearly identical with the model and in incurring the substantial costs of filing in the fifty states and Canada. It is not yet possible to estimate the financial savings and benefits that will accrue to North

⁴⁵ III: 39; IV: 20-21; V: 27-28; VI: 34-36; VII: 38-39.

⁴⁶ VII: 29-31, 55. See also Harold L. Roth and Walter W. Curley: Protection and Insurance. *Library Journal* 88: 4152-4156, November 1, 1963.

American libraries, when the policy becomes generally available, but these should be substantial.

Machine-Development — A Book Labeling System. Though various methods of marking the backstrips of books with call numbers are available to librarians, none has been wholly satisfactory. Since 1959 LTP, with the Council's assistance, has addressed itself to developing a new method — one which would make it possible to mark books more rapidly, uniformly, efficiently, ineradicably and economically than was then possible. Such a system has been developed for LTP by the Battelle Memorial Institute, of Columbus, Ohio, modified with the experience of field tests, and within the past several months has been placed on the market under the registered trade mark "Se-Lin."⁴⁷

The imprinting mechanism involves use of a typewriter, a thin but tough label, a protective overcoating which shields the label from wear and smudging, and an unusually strong adhesive which affixes the label to the binding so strongly that in most instances the surface of the binding is destroyed in separating the label from it. The labels must be affixed with a heated tacking iron to secure an instant bond, but the operation is simple, fast and clean.

Photocopying — Book Copying Devices. LTP's first separate publication in this field, W. R. Hawken's *Photocopying from Bound Volumes* has gone into its third printing. During the past year LTP published two supplements, each describing and evaluating three new copying devices intended for copying from bound volumes.⁴⁸

Photocopying — Microfiches. The advantages of microfiches (microfilm in card format) have long been apparent to some, but until very recently such use as they enjoyed was confined to Europe. Two and a half years ago an important application was announced by the publishers of Thomas'

⁴⁷ Norman H. Gaber: Book Marking Analysis, *Library Journal* 89: 1503-1507, April 1, 1964; The Development and Testing of a New Book Marking System. *Ibid.* 89: 1911-1913, May 1, 1964.

Gladys T. Piez: Book Marking System Marketed. *ALA Bulletin* 58: 410-411, May 1964; LTP Book Labeling System Goes to Market. *Ibid.* 58: 554-556, June 1964.

⁴⁸ W. R. Hawken. *Photocopying from Bound Volumes* . . . Chicago, Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1962. 208 p. Ill.; Supplement No. 1 . . . 1963. 32 p. Ill.; Supplement No. 2 . . . 1964 12 p. Ill.

Register of Manufacturers, using microfiches in a format (4 x 6 in.) which had not until then been generally used for any microform, transparent or opaque.

With a view to exploring the possibilities of standardization (so as to head off the danger to libraries of having to supply viewing equipment suitable for microfiches in a number of different formats) LTP commissioned a manual of microfiche practice from Mr. Hawken.⁴⁹ This was in December 1962. However, before the study could be completed, microfiches were adopted in still another and unrecognized format by a principal Government agency. The proposed manual was out of the question, but the work Mr. Hawken had done has contributed to the abandonment of the unrecognized format in favor of one which has international recognition.⁵⁰ This work will also be reflected in the manual of photocopying methods which is discussed next.

Photocopying — Manual. The library world has for some time been in need of a work that would bring up to date Herman H. Fussler's *Photographic Reproduction for Libraries* (1942) as well as Robert C. Binkley's *Manual on Methods of Reproducing Research Materials* (1931, 1936) and the International Federation for Documentation *Manual on Document Reproduction and Selection* (1953-8). After meetings of experts to define the table of contents of a replacement, the Council in March 1964 made a grant to enable LTP to commission Mr. Hawken to write such a book. It will be addressed not only to library administrators and directors of photoduplication services but also to others seeking information on the organization, staffing, equipment and operation of photocopying services. Publication is expected in 1966.

Testing — Record Players. In 1962 the Library Technology Project published a report — now out of print — on record players.⁵¹ Inasmuch as there is still considerable variation in

⁴⁹ VII: 38.

⁵⁰ W. R. Hawken: Technical Reports on Microfiche — What Price Utilization? *National Micro-News* (Journal of National Microfilm Association) 69: 195-207, April 1964.

———: Agreement to Standardize Microfiche. *ALA Bulletin* 58: 648-9, July-August 1964.

⁵¹ *The Testing and Evaluation of Record Players for Libraries: a Report Based on a Study Conducted for the Library Technology Project by Consumers' Research, Inc.* Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, [1962]. 76 p.

the quality of makes and models of record players now on the market, a new series of tests was commissioned this past year to provide up-to-date information. The findings will be published.

Testing — Miscellaneous. In addition to the projects mentioned above, LTP engages in a variety of testing and evaluating projects relating to library operations. Among the subjects of investigation during the past year have been: protective film coatings for microfilm; book truck casters for use on carpeted floors; book label adhesives; electric erasers; and type sizes and faces most suitable for persons with limited vision. The results of these and other investigations appear in LTP's columns in the *ALA Bulletin* and *Special Libraries*, or elsewhere,⁵² and direct inquiry can also be made of LTP itself.

Standardization in Library Work. The American Standards Association's Sectional Committee Z-39, Standards in Library Work and Documentation, was organized in 1939. It is currently sponsored by the Council of National Library Associations. The Committee acts as the American affiliate of a similar body of the International Standards Organization, and the New York Public Library is host institution to the Committee's secretariat. In 1961 the Council made a grant to the New York Public Library, matching a similar one from the National Science Foundation, to provide the Committee with secretariat services.⁵³ These grants were renewed for the past year. The Committee has given particular attention to the bibliographical aspects of library work and documentation, joining with others in developing standards for such matters as citation, indexing, abbreviations and transliteration.⁵⁴

Instruction in the Use of the Library — Teaching Machines. New members of the Mt. San Antonio Community College student body are given 50 minutes orientation in the use of the

⁵² For example, in LTP's column in the *ALA Bulletin* will be found discussion of vacuum cleaners (57: 672-673, July-August 1963), book label adhesives (57: 1051-1052, December 1963); suitable type for those of limited vision (58: 324-325, April 1964); and electric erasers (58: 412, May 1964). Among other reports are: Gladys T. Piez: Film Coatings — Do They Really Protect Microfilm? *National Micro-News* 67: 125-139, December 1963; and by the same author: Casters for Book Trucks — What Type is Best for Carpeted Floors? *ALA Bulletin* 57: 787-789, September 1963.

⁵³ VI: 34; VII: 39.

⁵⁴ Jerrold Orne: British and American Standards Associations Reach Agreement on a Draft Statement for Transliteration of Modern Russian. *Library Journal* 88: 4157-4160, November 1, 1963.

\$2 million library, completed and furnished in 1963. It has been found, however, that there is a continuing demand on the part of the students for follow-up instruction in the use of various library tools and facilities, and that in meeting this need the library staff uses time which is needed for other duties. Since the questions and instruction are repetitive, it is believed that the latter can be given just as efficiently by teaching machines. The Council has given the Walnut, California, institution a grant for the purchase and programming of five Videosonic teaching machines to test their effectiveness for the purpose. The machines will implement information stations at two tables where indexes are used, two subject card catalogs, and the main author-title card catalog. It is hoped that the programs which will be developed will be adaptable to use by other libraries; and in any case it is intended that a report shall be published.

Legal Problems Connected with Photocopying. In 1961 a "Single Copy Statement," asserting the traditional practice of libraries in making materials in their collections available by copy, was adopted by four principal national library associations (American Association of Law Libraries, American Library Association, Association of Research Libraries, Special Libraries Association) after completion of legal studies effected with the assistance of the Council.⁵⁵ Following this approval the Committee held further conferences with the publishers. As a result, and in view of the fact that a number of publishers have assigned copyrights for their out-of-print books to photocopying companies, the Committee modified its initial recommendation to take this situation in account. The amendment was likewise approved by all four of the constituent associations during the calendar year 1963. After all approvals were in, the Committee published a "Summary Statement of Policy."⁵⁶

During the year, also, a small grant was made to the Committee to Investigate Copyright Problems Affecting Communication in Science and Education to enable it to explore the feasibility of a "copyright clearing house" for handling permissions to copy.

⁵⁵ III: 38; V: 32, 48; VII: 53.

⁵⁶ Edward G. Freehafer: Summary Statement of Policy of the Joint Libraries Committee on Fair Use in Photocopying. *Special Libraries* 55:104-106, February 1964.

IV. PLANNING

A number of planning projects were begun or completed during the past year.

The Future of Library Work—The “Laboratory.” As described in its *Sixth Annual Report*, the Council moved to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel by the initiation of research directed by Dr. J. C. R. Licklider under a contract with Bolt Beranek and Newman Inc. of Cambridge, Massachusetts. The investigation commenced November 1, 1961.⁵⁷

The subject of the research was stated to be “‘the library of the 21st century’ or, more accurately, a system that may in the 21st century fulfill an integrated set of functions, the precursors of which are today served by libraries.”⁵⁸ The main aims of the first year’s effort were:

- To formulate agenda for planning, research and development.
- To develop a quantitative, functional description of libraries (and of the world’s fund of literature and knowledge), past and present, and to study the extrapolation of that description into the future.
- To formulate a statement of the functions that should be fulfilled by library systems and to derive from that formulation criteria in terms of which improvements in performance can be evaluated.
- To examine the areas of technology that now support or constrain library functions and the areas of science and technology in which advances must be made to support the library functions of the future . . . to select critical problem areas . . . to define objectives for research and development in those areas.
- To make a fundamental analysis of aims, methods and problems (a) in information storage and retrieval and (b) in memory organization penetrating in so far as possible through the particulars of present and envisioned

⁵⁷ VI: 10:11.

⁵⁸ Bolt Beranek and Newman Inc.: *Research on Concepts and Problems of Libraries of the Future*. Proposal No. P61-EP-20. Cambridge, Massachusetts, 15 August 1961. p. 1.

information processing technology to the basic understanding required in reshaping the technology to meet future requirements.

—To perform research on problems (a) in man-machine communication, (b) in machine processing of language, and (c) in “artificial intelligence” that are fundamental to effective automation of certain library functions.

The work-program laid out for the execution of these aims enumerated no fewer than eight separate publishable reports, five laboratory reports and four memoranda, all proposed to ensue from the first year’s work.

An advisory Committee on the Laboratory was named; it met four times during the first year of the project.

The contract was renewed for the year commencing November 1, 1962. For this year it was agreed that efforts should converge, and the aims accordingly contemplated work in two areas only:

- Organization of memory
- Man-machine communication.

At this time the director of the project, Dr. Licklider, accepted a temporary assignment in Washington. It was arranged, nevertheless, that he should continue to supervise the project during its second year, and work progressed on the topics designated for concentration of effort. At the end of the period a terminal report was rendered, covering the work of both years.⁵⁹

The report is in three sections. The “Introduction” describes the defects of the present system of storing and recording information which led to the study and the assumptions under which it was presented. “Man’s Interaction with Recorded Knowledge” reports the results of inquiries regarding the quantity of information which is required to be handled (corresponding at the present to 100 million miles of printed text) and the capabilities of computers for handling this information. It introduces the “procognitive” system of the future, which will not suffer from present limitations but will go

⁵⁹ Bolt Beranek and Newman Inc.: *Research on Concepts and Problems of Libraries of the Future, Final Report*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1963. 276 p. Processed. (Report No. 11101). See also Bolt Beranek and Newman Inc.: *Toward the Library of the 21st Century. A report of Progress Made in a Program of Research Sponsored by the Council on Library Resources*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1964. 42 p.

much further in organizing information and in ways of furnishing it. It lists 25 requirements to be made of the "pro-cognitive" system, gives an hypothetical example of its use, lists the steps which must be taken to achieve it, evaluates the state of the several arts which might be employed and indicates the points at which research and development are needed.

The last section of the report summarizes the findings of 12 studies⁶⁰ carried out under the contract, each of which is the subject of a separate report and a number of which have been or will be published. Some of these have to do with the state of computer art in relation to library functions; others with improvements of this art; and still others with specific experiments and studies in computer applications to information processing.

The report as a whole represents an imaginative conception of the manner in which man, profiting by his ability to manipulate records electronically, may in the future make use of recorded knowledge. It is obvious, however, that the attainment of the projected system will involve the prior solution of some tremendous problems at enormous costs and the expenditure of much time. But, as the report states (p. 45), "The few . . . who have had the opportunity to interact intimately ('on-line'

⁶⁰ J. C. R. Lickliger and W. E. Clark: On-Line Man-Computer Communication. *Proceedings of American Federation of Information Processing Societies* 21: 113-128, 1962.

Daniel G. Bobrow and others: Syntactic Analysis of English by Computer — A Survey. *Ibid.* 24: 365-387, 1963.

John A. Swets: Information Retrieval Systems. *Science* 141: 245-50, July 19, 1963.

John W. Senders: Information Storage Requirements for the Contents of the World's Libraries. *Ibid.* 141: 1067-8, September 13, 1963.

Fischer S. Black: *A Question-Answering System: QAS-5*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Bolt Beranek and Newman Inc., 1963. 85 p. Processed. (Report No. 1063.)

———: *Specific Question-Answering System*. *Ibid.*, 1963. 26 p. Processed.

Daniel G. Bobrow and others: *A Computer-Program System to Facilitate the Study of Technical Documents*. *Ibid.*, 1963. 12 p. Processed. (Report No. 1103.)

Lewis C. Clapp: *Associative Chaining as an Information Retrieval Technique*. *Ibid.*, 1963. 26 p. Processed. (Report No. 1079.)

Mario Grignetti: *Computer Aids to Literature Searches*. *Ibid.*, 1963. 10 p. Processed. (Report No. 1074.)

———: *On the Entropy of Words in Printed English*. *Ibid.*, 6 p. Processed. (Report No. 1073.)

———: *On the Length of a Class of Serial Files*. *Ibid.*, 1963. 26 p. Processed. (Report No. 1011.)

Thomas Marill: *Libraries and Question-Answering Systems*. *Ibid.*, 1963. 40 p. Processed (Report No. 1071.)

in a good, flexible system) with a computer and its programs and data . . . are excited about the prospect and eager to move into the procognitive future . . .”

The Library of Congress — Possibilities of Automation. The problems of the Library of Congress are those of size and number. Its more than 43 million items fill two enormous buildings and need a third; it sells 46 million catalog cards a year and returns over \$3 million a year to the United States Treasury; and it costs \$23 million a year in appropriated funds alone to operate. Other libraries have become heavily dependent upon its bibliographic services which are made available through publication in various forms.

This library of course makes use of mechanical devices to the full extent that they are applicable, and accordingly they are omnipresent. Thus, it has been presumptive that for an operation which is essentially one of data processing, the data processing automata should be applicable. But a puzzle has been where to begin: the operations are so interrelated that tinkering with one could well be disastrous for others. Nor has it been clear just what improvements could be brought by automation to the operations of a great research library and of other libraries sharing its services. Surveys by three major companies specializing in computer applications failed to produce answers to these questions. It consequently was decided to procure a survey by a specially-recruited team of outstanding experts. The Council made a grant in aid.⁶¹

The team was headed by Dr. Gilbert W. King, until 1963 Director of Research of the International Business Machines Corporation, thereafter Vice President of the Itek Corporation.⁶² It collectively possessed a background of work in the fields of information retrieval, computer theory and design, mathematical linguistics, automatic translation, indexing and abstracting techniques. Also assisting was an advisory committee of leading American librarians.⁶³ Henry J. Dubester, Chief of the Library's General Reference and Bibliography Division, served as project coordinator.

⁶¹ V: 29.

⁶² Other members: Harold P. Edmundson, Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.; Merrill M. Flood, University of Michigan; Manfred Kochen, International Business Machines Corporation; Richard L. Libby, Itek Corporation; Don R. Swanson, University of Chicago Graduate Library School; and Alexander Wylly, Planning Research Corporation.

⁶³ Herman H. Fussler, University of Chicago; Edward M. Heiliger, Florida Atlantic University; Frank B. Rogers, University of Colorado Medical Center and Frederick H. Wagman, University of Michigan.

LOOKING FORWARD. Feasible first steps toward a system of automating the Library of Congress, and perhaps of a national system of interlinked research libraries, were described by Dr. Gilbert W. King at a press conference held in the Library's Woodrow Wilson Room this past January. Facing the reporters and editors are: Mr. Henry J. Dubester, detailed by the Library to serve as coordinator of the investigation; Dr. King, Vice President and Director of Research of the Itek Corporation, who headed the survey team; Librarian of Congress L. Quincy Mumford; and Deputy Librarian of Congress Rutherford D. Rogers.

This past February the committee's work was finished and its report was made public.⁶⁴

The report visualizes a future day when automation of the Library of Congress can provide benefits in which all libraries electing to use its services may participate, and of which library users even at great distances will be the ultimate beneficiaries.

Specifically it contemplates that the various catalogs of the Library of Congress will be so mechanized that they can be consulted electronically (on viewing screens) with convenience to the user and subject to his complete manipulation; and that the collections to which the catalogs refer will themselves be so mechanized through photographic or electronic micro-reproduction as to place them within the individual user's electronic control.

The report was backed up by a number of (unpublished) costing studies of the Library's operations.

It is not to be expected that this report should be able to describe in specific terms the future aspect of a system of fantastic size and complexity for which there exists as yet scarcely one piece of appropriate equipment. The usefulness of the report derives rather from its success in presenting the situation in broad terms, in indicating the manner and magnitude of the modifications which automation may be expected to effect, in estimating the costs involved and the balances of saving or of additional expense, and in suggesting a method of approach. Its significance, in consequence, is in getting the question off dead center.

Designing the Machine-Readable Bibliographic Record. When the survey of the possibilities of automation at the Library of Congress had progressed to the point where it was possible to discern some of the techniques which would be needed to make such a system possible, the Council commissioned Mr. Lawrence F. Buckland of Inforonics Inc., to make a brief investigation and report, in collaboration with the staff of the Library of Congress, on the simplest effective method for converting bibliographic data from graphic to such machine-readable form as to meet all foreseeable typographic and bibliographic needs.

⁶⁴ Gilbert W. King and others: *Automation and the Library of Congress. A survey sponsored by the Council on Library Resources, Inc.* Washington: Library of Congress, 1963 [1964]. 88 p.

Mr. Buckland reported⁶⁵ the conclusion that the requirement could be met by typewriter-produced perforated paper tape, using suitable codes to identify the various bibliographic and typographic elements. Accordingly, the Council has newly commissioned Mr. Buckland (again in collaboration with the Library of Congress and also with the Government Printing Office which prints the Library's catalog cards) to demonstrate the validity of the conclusion.

It is expected, upon completion of this demonstration, to offer the codes that will be developed as the basis for a standard for converting bibliographic information to machine-readable form, so as to achieve compatibility of product and avoid duplication of effort in this area of activity.

The Federal Governmental Libraries. The circumstantial background and arrangements affecting the Brookings Institution study of the libraries of the Federal Government undertaken in 1959 have been described in an earlier report.⁶⁶ The investigation was carried into 1961 by Dr. Luther H. Evans, formerly Librarian of Congress, more recently Director General of Unesco, and presently Director of International and Legal Collections at Columbia University. Thereafter, arrangements for a small conference to discuss the recommendations emerging from the survey, and the editing of the final report were effected by Dr. Harold Orlans of the Brookings Institution.⁶⁷

The report contains nearly a score of recommendations. The principal of these is still, as it has been at least since Melvil Dewey made it (probably not for the first time) to the Congressional Joint Committee on the Library in 1896, that there should be a Federal library council to assist in coordinating the work of the Federal libraries. The principal obstacles to the execution of this recommendation have always been the unequal status of the libraries (some of which are mere offices while one, at least, is a separate agency) and their seclusion behind the barriers which separate the Executive, Legislative and Judicial Establishments.

⁶⁵ Lawrence F. Buckland: *The Creation of a Machine Record of Library of Congress Catalog Data for Distribution and Automatic Typesetting of Cards and Book Form Catalogs*. Maynard, Massachusetts: Inforonics, Inc., 1964. 15 p. Processed.

⁶⁶ III: 40-1.

⁶⁷ Luther H. Evans and others: *Federal Departmental Libraries; A Summary Report of a Survey and a Conference*. Washington: The Brookings Institution [1963]. x, 150 p.

It might not be easy to find a formula for overcoming these difficulties so as to permit the reaching and execution of meaningful decisions, and it was for its expertise in such matters of governmental organization that the Brookings Institution was selected for the study in the first place. At the present writing a genuine effort appears to be underway to find such a formula in accordance with the recommendations of the report.

The State Governments — Library Functions. In providing assistance to the Third Assembly on the Library Functions of the States which was held at the Library of Congress in November 1963, the Council once more⁶⁸ facilitated discussions between state and Federal officers responsible for library planning. Exclusive of personnel from the host institution, more than a hundred persons participated from all parts of the nation; and not only was the personal attendance larger but there was a wider representation of organizations than in the past. A report has been issued.⁶⁹

Junior Colleges and their Libraries. There are more than 700 junior (or community) colleges in the United States, and they are expected to increase at the rate of 30-40 a year for the next decade. An increasing proportion of all students in institutions of higher learning may be expected to be found in these colleges. But modest as are the library requirements set for these institutions by the American Library Association (a minimum of 20,000 volumes), the typical junior college library has scarcely half of this number.

What are the realities of need and use? An inquiry would seem to be in order. To explore the desirability and conditions of such an inquiry the Council, in cooperation with the American Association of Junior Colleges, convened a meeting in Washington, February 17-18, 1964, attended by presidents and librarians of junior colleges as well as others concerned and involved. A consensus was reached as to the desirability and general conditions of an inquiry, a report of the meeting has been distributed,⁷⁰ and support for the inquiry is being sought.

⁶⁸ III: 44; V: 55, nos. 137, 138.

⁶⁹ Mary A. McKenzie: *Proceedings of the Third Assembly on the Library Functions of the States, Held November 13-15, 1963*. Washington: Library of Congress, Exchange and Gift Division, 1964. 103 p. Processed.

⁷⁰ *Strengthening Library Services in Junior College Education: Summary of Discussion . . . February 17-18, 1964*. Washington: Council On Library Resources, Inc., 1964. 7 p. Processed.

Arkansas — College Libraries. With assistance from the Rockefeller Brothers Fund during a seven-year period, the seven member colleges⁷¹ of the Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges developed a cooperative library system involving division of responsibility for acquisition and the sharing of collections. In need of an outside appraisal of the effectiveness of the arrangements, with a view to extending or curtailing them, the Foundation was given a grant by the Council for a survey of the cooperative effort.⁷² The services of Dr. Robert B. Downs, Dean of Library Administration at the University of Illinois, were obtained. His report has now been published.⁷³ Of a number of recommendations the principal is that for the next three to five years the cooperative acquisition program emphasize periodicals and basic reference works.

California — A Cooperative Regional Science Library. Harvey Mudd, one of the Claremont Colleges, shares research library facilities with the others of the group. A science library is being planned. Because of burgeoning industrial development in the area it seemed wise at this stage of planning to explore the possibility that the new library, making use of automatic data processing devices, might be able to serve both the academic and industrial needs of the area.

The Council underwrote the cost of such an inquiry; both faculty and industry representatives participated in the investigation, which has been completed. The report⁷⁴ visualizes a cooperative library giving 24-hour service to industries and Federal establishments working in such fields as electronics, aerospace technology, missile systems, military systems, and the like. Service would be on a pro-rated subscription cost basis within a thousand-square-mile area in southern California. "There is an industrial need for a fast,

⁷¹ Arkansas College, Batesville; The College of the Ozarks, Clarksville; Harding College, Searcy; Hendrix College, Conway; John Brown University, Siloam Springs; Ouachita Baptist College, Arkadelphia; and Southern Baptist College, Walnut Ridge.

⁷² VI: 37, 39.

⁷³ Robert B. Downs: *Report on a Survey of the Libraries of the Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges.* [Little Rock, Arkansas], 1963. 44 p.

⁷⁴ *A Joint College/Industry Library With Automata. . . .* Prepared for Harvey Mudd College, Science and Engineering, Claremont, California, One of the Claremont Colleges. Washington, D. C.: Reprinted by The Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1964. [iv] 35 p. Processed.

effective service which can be offered, providing start-up support is obtained and enough subscribers are enlisted to cover annual costs," the report observes.

State-wide Coordination of Resources — New York. The Board of Regents of the State of New York has adopted a plan for state-wide coordination of library reference and research resources, and is moving towards its implementation through appropriation of the necessary funds. For this purpose preliminary studies of the effect of the application of the plan in various parts of the state are necessary. One such study had been performed for the Rochester area. However, it was most important that one be conducted in the New York City area, where the largest research and reference holdings and the greatest number of users are concentrated. To make it possible, the Council made a grant to the Brooklyn Public Library in behalf of an *ad hoc* committee of librarians headed by Mr. Francis R. St. John, at that time Chief Librarian of the Brooklyn library. The grant matched one made by the Old Dominion Foundation to the American Library Association in the committee's behalf. The study has been completed.⁷⁵ Among the recommendations made by the committee on the basis of the report are (a) the establishment of a New York Library Service Authority, a non-profit organization which would provide or sell any service of use to members and non-members, and initiate and coordinate research in library matters; (b) construction of an undergraduate college-oriented reference library in midtown Manhattan; and (c) identification and designation of advanced research collections on special subjects.

New York World's Fair — Conventional-Electronic Library. The exhibit presented by the American Library Association at the Century 21 Exposition, Seattle 1962, was the first participation by that organization in a world's fair since the Louisiana Purchase Exposition, St. Louis, 1904. The 1962 exhibit (the planning for which was made possible by a grant from the Council) was economically feasible only as a collaborative

⁷⁵ *Prospects for Library Cooperation in New York City, Planning for More Effective Utilization of Reference and Research Resources.* New York: Nelson Associates, Incorporated, 1963. [135 l.] Processed. Also: Report on New York Library Resources. *Special Libraries* 55: 106-107, February 1964.

presentation of library service in conventional forms combined with displays of recently adopted and still-experimental technical developments contributed by industrial producers.⁷⁶

“LIBRARY/USA.” Dialing book reviews is one of the innovations, some still experimental, featuring the American Library Association exhibit in the United States Pavilion at the New York World’s Fair.

The success of this collaboration, not only in creating an informative and lively exhibit but also in providing an opportunity for a large number of especially selected librarians to become acquainted and to work with the new devices, was so great as to ensure its repetition at the New York World’s Fair 1964-5. There the “Library/U.S.A.” exhibit has 7000 square feet of space in the United States Pavilion and includes an adult reading area, a children’s library, a reference service and a computer and communications section. The Council has contributed to the training (especially in working with the electronic devices) of the nearly 300 reference librarians brought from all parts of the United States to staff the exhibit.

Ohio — County Library Service. Peculiarities of state library legislation and arrangements for the support of libraries favor the establishment and maintenance of small local libraries in Ohio and discourage the formation of stronger units. Efforts to convince local groups of the economies and improved services which would be provided by larger units have been for the most part unavailing.

⁷⁶ V: 27; VI: 8-10.

Lorain County, with a population of 217,500 in 1960, was served by seven autonomous libraries, yet parts of its area of 495 square miles had no library service when, in November 1961, a grant was made to the Lorain County Public Library Organization to explore (at the suggestion of the County's budgeting officials and in collaboration with the State Librarian) whether a plan of county-wide library service might be developed that would be convincing to the affected groups.⁷⁷

A report of the survey has been published.⁷⁸ The surveyors conclude "that this study bears out the contentions of the experts and shows not only that the small library costs more than the library serving more people — but gives some clues as to why this is so." Regretfully, by the time the report was published, both the Elyria Public Librarian (Mr. Merlin D. Wolcott) and the Ohio State Librarian (Mr. Walter Brahm), under whose auspices the study had been launched, had accepted positions elsewhere.

Rhode Island — State Library Legislation. The publication of the Brown University Study of library service in Rhode Island,⁷⁹ prepared under a grant from the Council, was recorded in last year's report, as was also the small supplemental grant to assist in securing adoption of the recommendations contained in the Study.⁸⁰

It is gratifying to be able to record only a year later that through the joint efforts of educators, librarians and other community leaders, a major step has been taken, consisting of the establishment of a Department of State Library Services, with supporting appropriations, by act of the Assembly approved May 8, 1964.

International Federation for Documentation. This organization was established in 1895; its headquarters are in the Hague; and it has approximately 100 members in 36 countries; its principal activity is the maintenance of the Universal Decimal Classification, but it also publishes the *Revue Internationale de Documentation* and numerous important bibliog-

⁷⁷ VI: 40.

⁷⁸ Mildred W. Sandoe and others: *Lorain County Library Survey, Lorain County, Ohio.* Columbus, Ohio Library Foundation, 1963. [154 p.] Processed.

⁷⁹ John A. Humphry with the special assistance of Lucille Wickersham: *Library Cooperation, The Brown University Study of University School Community Library Coordination in the State of Rhode Island.* Providence, Rhode Island: Brown University Press, 1963. 228 p.

⁸⁰ IV: 19; VII: 35-36.

raphies, directories and guides; its American affiliate is the National Academy of Sciences-National Research Council, which extends participation in its affiliation to some thirty national organizations. Its thirty-first congress (the first to be held in the United States) is planned to meet in Washington, October 7-16, 1965. Anticipating results comparable to those which flowed from the International Conference on Scientific Information, 1958,⁸¹ the Council has made a grant to assist the congress.

Inventory of Research Needed in Library Work. In 1959 Dr. Robert D. Leigh, director of the Public Library Inquiry, 1947-1950, and at that time Dean of the School of Library Service of Columbia University, organized a Library Schools Committee for Research on Inter-Library Cooperation in the Public Library Field. The purpose of the Committee was to plan research in the area of interest so as to make maximum use of the slender resources available to the participants. The Council assisted the Committee's endeavors with a small grant⁸² but Dr. Leigh died in 1961 before conclusions were reported.

Recently, however, several members of the Committee have assembled the drafts which were prepared for its use, and from these have extracted and published a long list of topics of needed research, not only with respect to public libraries, but also to school, college and university and special libraries and to the problems of libraries generally.⁸³

⁸¹ II: 35-36; III: 43.

⁸² III: 44-45.

⁸³ Frank L. Schick, John C. Frantz and others. Library Science Research Needs. *Journal of Education for Librarianship* 3: 280-291, Spring 1963. Also reprinted by U. S. Office of Education, 1963.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Opinion of Independent Accountants

July 31, 1964

To the Board of Directors of

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1964 and its expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

**COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES
AND FUND BALANCE**

June 30, 1964

ASSETS

Cash		\$ 261,390
Investments:		
United States Treasury Bills, at cost (approximates market) \$ 979,067		
Savings account, including earned interest for the year of \$37,622	1,094,965	2,074,032
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation in annual installments of \$1,000,000 (Note)		4,000,000
Deposits		911
		<u>\$6,336,333</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable (see accompanying statement)		\$ 899,070
Accounts payable and withheld taxes		3,263
Fund balance:		
Balance June 30, 1963	\$6,541,806	
Deduct — Expenditures less income for the year (see accompanying statement)	1,107,806	
Balance June 30, 1964 (Note)		5,434,000
		<u>\$6,336,333</u>

NOTE

The installment for the year ending June 30, 1965 was received on June 25, 1964. The terms of the Grant from The Ford Foundation provide that \$200,000 annually is earmarked to assist the Council "to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel." At June 30, 1964 \$1,175,957 of the Fund Balance is earmarked for this purpose. Also, \$247,409 has been appropriated for other specific grants and contracts and \$7,309 has been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts to be made at his discretion.

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1964

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects (see accompanying statement)	\$1,037,948	
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded (see accompanying statement)	<u>35,271</u>	\$1,002,677
General administrative expense:		
Compensation and employee benefits	123,223	
Rent	7,500	
Professional services	3,161	
Travel and meetings	7,625	
Furniture and equipment	1,023	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	<u>14,866</u>	<u>157,398</u>
		\$1,160,075

INCOME

From investments	<u>52,269</u>
Expenditures less income	<u><u>\$1,107,806</u></u>

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1964

	Payable June 30, 1963	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1964
American Association of Law Libraries Advisory Committee on Project Lawsearch		\$ 777		\$ 777	
American Association of Law Schools Preparation of book selection lists for law school libraries		54,000		27,000	\$ 27,000
American Bar Foundation Automatic indexing of legal literature	\$ 15,000			15,000	
American Library Association Compilation of a list of non-Government Printing Office Federal Government Publications		5,000		5,000	
Completion of ALA Catalog Code	17,550	30,468		32,550	15,468
Coordination of library statistics	24,480			24,480	
Foreign survey of the Dewey Decimal Classification	20,000				20,000
Library Technology Project Development of improved board for archival containers			\$ 3,276	(3,276)	
Development of performance standards for library bookbinding — Phase II	18,686	21,600		30,286	10,000
Extension of Library Technology Project to April 1, 1961			565	(565)	
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1962			2,365	(2,365)	
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1963	33,757		7,302	26,455	
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1964		120,000		120,000	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1964		100,000		29,050	70,950
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1965		130,000			130,000
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1965		100,000			100,000
Preparation of a new edition of the Guide to Microfilming Practices			109	(109)	
Publication of a book-selection service at the college library level	150,000			50,000	100,000
Scholarships for staffing ALA reference library at New York World's Fair 1964-1965		20,000			20,000
Support of the ALA International Relations Office	71,716			31,509	40,207
American Library Association (co-sponsor with Association of Research Libraries) Preparation of a book on the planning of college/university library buildings	35,365			23,365	12,000
Assembly on the Library Functions of the States, Program Committee Assistance toward Third Meeting, Washington, D. C., November 13-15, 1963		1,500		1,500	

	Payable June 30, 1963	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1964
Association of Research Libraries					
Programs for coordinated acquisition of library research materials.....		\$ 3,300	\$ 823	\$ 2,477	
Survey of original cataloging performed in American research libraries.....		5,000			\$ 5,000
Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges					
Re-evaluation of the cooperative library system of the members of the Foundation..			89	(89)	
W. J. Barrow Laboratory					
Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relating to preservation of books and other library materials	\$ 13,881	120,000		55,309	78,572
Bell & Howell Company					
Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography.....	73,442			59,352	14,090
Bolt Beranek and Newman, Inc.					
Research on concepts and problems of libraries of the future					
1961-1962	35,141			35,141	
1962-1963	93,211			93,211	
Brooklyn Public Library					
Survey of reference-research library resources and organization in New York City.....		16,000		16,000	
Capital Graphic Systems, Inc.					
Feasibility of simplified lithographic process for catalog card reproduction.....	4,000			4,000	
Specification-design study of lithographic duplicator for library catalog cards.....		5,000			5,000
Carson Laboratories					
Demonstration of high density crystalline photo-storage	51,274	35,959		62,274	24,959
The de Florez Company, Inc.					
Field test of automatic book-cradle/ page-turner	1,333				1,333
Working model of a book-copying cradle/press.	929				929
Working model of a catalog card duplicator...	2,314				2,314
Committee to Investigate Copyright Problems					
Affecting Communication in Science and Education					
Feasibility study of a copyright clearinghouse in connection with photoreproduction.....		700		700	
Coordination of cataloging rules*		200		54	146
Documentation, Inc.					
Development of a portable inexpensive reader- printer for microcopies.....		33,000			33,000
Drexel Institute of Technology					
Preparation of a manual on work simplification in small libraries.....	21,095				21,095
Expenses of testing a coordinate index to legal literature*	4,068			559	3,509

* Council-administered project.

	Payable June 30, 1963	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1964
Expenses connected with the study of concepts and problems of libraries of the future*.....	\$ 946	\$ 10,000		\$ 6,563	\$ 4,383
Harvey Mudd College					
Study of the bases, including the use of the techniques of automata, for providing the capability of a science library for academic-industry service		5,000		5,000	
Inforonics, Inc.					
Investigation of the creation of a machine-readable record of Library of Congress catalog data					
Phase I		3,000	\$ 1,919	1,081	
Phase II		37,067			37,067
Institute for Scientific Information					
Feasibility study of the Copywriter.....	10,000			10,000	
Intectron Incorporated					
Investigation of factors affecting high-reduction microphotography	733				733
International Federation for Documentation.					
Secretariat,					
31st Meeting and Congress, Washington, D. C., October 1965					
Support of Meeting.....		10,000			10,000
Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials, Inc.					
Assistance toward placing the record of serials in libraries in the United States and Canada on a continuing basis (supplemental grant)..		25,326		25,326	
Jonker Business Machines, Inc.					
Construction of production model of Minimatrix Camera	2,000			2,000	
Lewis and Clark College					
Pilot project for development of annotated bibliographies for area studies at undergraduate level		1,500		1,500	
Library Association, London					
Survey of major indexing and abstracting services for library science and documentation		2,000		2,000	
Library of Congress					
Creation of a national union catalog of manuscript collections (supplement).....		70,565		35,000	35,565
Development of a national plan for scholarly photocopying		5,689		5,689	
Planning a national conference on mechanization in libraries.....			167	(167)	
Services of the U. S. Government Printing Office in connection with the investigation of the creation of a machine record of Library of Congress catalog data.....		10,000		5,000	5,000
Study of possibilities of mechanization in large research libraries	20,000		12,343	(12,343)	20,000
Travel grant to enable Director and Assistant Director of the Archives of France to visit the U. S.		2,500		2,500	

* Council-administered project.

	Payable June 30, 1963	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1964
Lorain County Public Library Organization A survey of the public libraries of Lorain County, Ohio			\$ 141	\$ (141)	
Meeting to discuss a study of junior college libraries*		\$5,000	1,354	3,646	
Mt. San Antonio College Development of teaching-machine programs for instruction in the use of the library.....		4,650		4,650	
Music Library Association Participation of Music Library Association in meeting of International Cataloging Code Commission of the International Association of Music Libraries, August 1964.....		750	127	623	
To record the holdings of American Libraries for inclusion in the International Inventory of Musical Sources	\$ 13,650				\$ 13,650
Pan American Union Compilation and publication of a subject heading list in Spanish.....		25,000		12,500	12,500
Photo Devices, Inc. Engineering and resources study of production of microcopy projector for private use.....		1,500		1,500	
Photogrammetry, Inc. Design and fabrication of prototypes of a scholar's camera and monocular viewer.....	8,626			8,626	
Society of American Archivists A study of state archives (supplement).....		3,897		3,897	
Stanford University Survey of methods for producing catalogs in book form.....		3,500		3,500	
Syracuse University Development of programs in information storage and retrieval.....			1,250	(1,250)	
United States National Bureau of Standards Experiments in automatic indexing.....		5,000		5,000	
University of Chicago Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600				24,600
University of Pittsburgh Conference on Automation and Library Planning, June 1964.....		3,500		3,500	
Searching statutory law by computer.....	29,443			29,443	
Yale University Development and demonstration of the basis, operation and results of the Yale University Library's selective book retirement program			3,441	(3,441)	
	\$797,240	\$1,037,948	\$35,271	\$900,847	\$899,070

* Council-administered project.

A C K N O W L E D G M E N T S

The picture of the scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the front cover, is taken from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . .*, Paris, 1588. The picture on the back cover is reproduced from the page of text facing the engraving.

The pattern on the inside of the cover, front and back, is of a bank of card catalog drawers in the Library of Congress Annex, and was taken by George Lohr. The design on the transparency inside the cover is that of the master memory pattern found in various International Business Machines computers. The diagram of an automated library system appearing on the transparency in the middle of the Annual Report is reproduced from *Automation and the Library of Congress* (Washington: The Library of Congress, 1963), by permission, as is the picture of the press conference held at the Library on January 22, 1964, to announce publication of the report.

The picture of the system for dialing book reviews at "Library/USA" at the New York World's Fair was taken by Jack Tyler. The picture of the clamp binder, for perfect binding, being used by Edward Belanger of the Catholic University of America Libraries staff, was taken by the George Lohr Studio, which also designed this Report.

The Report is printed on a stable and enduring paper, "Permalife."

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FUNCTIONAL BLOCK DIAGRAM OF AN AUTOMATED LIBRARY SYSTEM

Este cy est vne belle & artificieuse machine, laquelle est fort utile & commode à toute personne qui se delecte à l'estude, principalement à ceux qui sont mal dispos & subiects aux gouttes; car avec ceste sorte de machiné vn homme peut voir & lire vne grande quantité de liures, sans se mouuoir d'un lieu: outre, elle porte avec soy vne belle commodité, qui est de tenir & occuper peu de place, au lieu où on la met, comme tout homme d'entendement peut bien comprendre par son dessein. Ceste rouë est faicte avec l'artifice que on voit, à sçauoir, elle est construite de telle maniere, qu'en mettât les liures sur les tablettes, combien qu'on tourne ladicte rouë tout autour, iamais lesdits liures ne tomberont, ni se remueront du lieu où ils sont posés, ains demeureront tousiours en vn mesme estat, & se représenteront deuant le lecteur en la mesme maniere qu'ils ont esté mis sur les tablettes. Ceste rouë se peut faire grande & petite, selon la volonté de celuy qui la faict faire, obseruant toutesfois les proportions de chascune partie des artifices de ladicte rouë, comme il pourra fort bien faire, considerant diligemment toutes les parties de ceste petite rouë, & les autres artifices qui se voyent en icelle machine: lesquelles parties sont faictes par mesures & proportions. Et pour donner plus grande intelligence & cognoissance à vn chascun qui desirera faire mettre en ceuvre ladicte machine, j'ay mis icy à part & descouuert tous les artifices qui sont requis en telle machine, afin qu'un chascun les puisse mieux comprendre, & s'en seruir à son besoin.

